

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

An IOC Newsletter on toxic algae and algal blooms

No. 21

Mitigation in HAB Research

At the very beginning of HAB research, there was no "M": we just investigated red tides, usually in panic, as they came along and caused havoc. Now there are three. We started **Monitoring**: taking samples and measurements on a more-or-less routine basis around certain coasts to detect incipient harmful blooms, and follow both the occurrence and, we hoped, the dynamics, of the algae which cause them. In order to get a better idea of where HABs come from and how they develop, this soon expanded to monitoring the occurrence of algae and ancillary data at sea from ships, aircraft and satellites. Later, we learnt to do **Management**: taking steps to prevent them doing harm. These steps include information campaigns, whether they be for the general public or for groups such as fish farmers, planning site-selection strategies, including those to design and relocate fish

cages for HAB avoidance, early harvesting procedures, and so on. (Measures to control the introduction and transfer of marine organisms (ITMO) are not counted here). More recently, we have started **Mitigation**. In the field of HABs, the word "mitigation" is used in two distinct ways. Mitigation *sensu lato* is used to mean reduction of the effects of HABs by all means, by monitoring, management of all types, and information programmes for both public and professionals. Mitigation *sensu stricto* is taken here to mean reduction of harmful effects, ways of making blooms less harmful when they do occur, despite any monitoring or management we may (or may not) have done.

The successive rise in the three M's

To illustrate the successive rise in these three activities I perused the

proceedings of the series of World Red Tide and HAB scientific conferences starting with that in Takamatsu, Japan. Figure 1 shows the results.

Monitoring: There were three papers on monitoring at Takamatsu (1987), one at Lund (1989), and a jump to 19 at Rhode Island (1991). That it has remained at this high level (12 to 24) since, may reflect a constancy in novel types of monitoring, since absolute levels of monitoring worldwide appear to be increasing markedly. **Management**: The first paper I counted on management, by Wong (Takamatsu [1]) described an action scheme implemented in Hong Kong. I could find none either at Lund (1989) or Rhode I. (1991), but after Nantes (1993) where there was one, the number of papers on management has increased steadily, reaching 13 at Hobart (2000) (Fig. 1). **Mitigation**: Although at

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◆ Republic of Korea

Inter-state symposium on harmful algal blooms and clays

An Inter-state symposium on "harmful algal blooms and clays" was held on 30 May 2000 at the National Fisheries Research and Development Institute (NFRDI) in Pusan, Korea, under the auspices of NFRDI and sponsored by the Ministry of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries of Korea. The symposium was attended by more than 100 participants from Korea, China, and USA. The objectives were to evaluate the mitigation capability of clays on harmful algae blooms and their impacts on marine ecosystems.

Eleven papers were presented in 3 sessions: (1) Properties and application of clays, (2) Mitigation capability and impacts of clays, (3) Evaluation of clay dispersal and new techniques for mitigation.

Interest focussed on the following issues; "Recent approaches on the

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Nantes (1993), Yang and Albright presented a paper on mitigation of the harmful effects of the diatom *Chaetoceros* on salmon gills, they published elsewhere [2], and we had to wait until Vigo (1997) to see the first publication about mitigation in the HAB proceedings. It was by Hak Gyoon Kim, who presented strategies for mitigating the effects of *Cochlodinium* blooms in Korea by spreading clay and loess. At Hobart (2000), the number of abstracts on mitigation rose to ten, of which two were about cyanobacteria. The paper by Lu Songhui *et al.* [3], which referred to the moving of rafts as mitigation, I have counted under management.

Recent progress in Mitigation *sensu stricto*

Preparing the way: The sharp increase in the number of mitigation papers reflects growing interest in the subject, and its encouragement by HAB working groups and panels. In 1997, in "Turning back the harmful red tide", Anderson [4], (using the term "mitigation" *sensu lato*), pointed out that while HABs were already a serious and increasing problem in marine waters, scientists and funding agencies had been slow to investigate possible control strategies. Barely three years later, the tide is turning. For instance, we have now seen the "First Conference on Harmful Algae Management and Mitigation" at Subic Bay, Philippines, hosted by Rhodora Azanza and chaired by Sherwood Hall [5]. On the home page of The IOC Harmful Algal Bloom Programme [6], we see "The overall goal of the HAB Programme: To foster the effective management of, and scientific research on, harmful algal blooms in order to understand their causes, predict their occurrences, and mitigate their effects" (my italics).

Mitigation techniques relative to finfish survival: At the Hobart meeting, not including communications expressing intentions and future needs for mitigation, I counted ten oral papers on the results of mitigation work. However there were no posters. Why not? Did the lack of posters reflect the importance and novelty of the field, as considered by the Selection Committee? The mitigation techniques described fell into the following categories.

Clay was the big subtopic in mitigation. H.G. Kim [7] had started the topic rolling at the Vigo conference with the effects of montmorillonite and loess on *Cochlodinium polykrikoides* blooms. He found montmorillonite the more efficacious of the two, with 90% of the *Cochlodinium*

removed after 60 minutes' exposure to a concentration of 2 g/L montmorillonite. No less than thirty types of clay were tested by Sengco *et al.* [8] for their capacity to flocculate and sediment different HAB species. With some combinations, removal efficiencies as high as 80%, for instance with *Pfiesteria*, could be achieved with clay concentrations as low as 30g/m³, while 100% mortality of precipitated *Gymnodinium breve* was achieved with 50 g/m³ of phosphatic clay. Surfactants, particularly polyaluminium chloride (PAC), which is approved for drinking water, tended to increase removal efficiency by nearly an order of magnitude. PAC also decreased the tendency for the nutrients NO₃, NO₂, NH₄, PO₄, and SiO₄ to diffuse out of the clay flocs, which could otherwise fuel HAB regrowth. Cell removal in some cases was increased by agitating the water, but reduced with increasing salinity and with increasing cell concentration. Yu Zhiming *et al.* [9] also presented the results of coagulation tests, with derived models, for different clays and algae, and investigated the effects of surfactants such as PAC, mixed metal layered hydroxide, and pH. Zhiming *et al.*, like Sengco *et al.*, found montmorillonite to be a good flocculator, but suggested kaolin is even better.

Sodium hypochlorite: A study was presented by H.R. Kim *et al.* [10] on the effect sodium hypochlorite NaOCl, generated by electrolysis *in situ*. It was found to reduce markedly the concentrations of various HAB dinoflagellates at an NaOCl concentration of ~0.4 g/m³. On the other hand, copepods remained unaffected at concentrations up to 3 g/m³. Under bright sunlight, half the NaOCl was converted to NaCl. So it was suggested that this technique could reduce concentrations of red tide dinoflagellates, while secondary effects on ciliates and copepods would be minimal. Treatment costs were estimated at ~US\$70,000/km², mainly to set up the equipment.

Cysteine compounds: In Vigo, Jenkinson and Arzul [11] reported methods to measure both the rheotoxicity (toxic action due to rheological thickening of the water) and the cytotoxicity to fish of substances secreted by *Gymnodinium mikimotoi* and two other algae. They also showed how the rheological and cytological components contributed to total ichthyotoxicity. At Hobart the same authors [12] described how they used similar methods to investigate the cytotoxicity and rheotoxicity to fish of two fish-killing algae, *G. mikimotoi* from Brittany (predominantly rheotoxic) and *Gymnodinium*

cf *maguelonense* from Tunisia (predominantly cytotoxic due to active oxygen radicals). They then tested three cysteine compounds added to the water on the different types of toxicity and fish-killing power. In both these harmful algae, they found that the cysteine compounds mitigate both types of toxicity. The estimated cost of treatment would be less than US\$1/tonne of fish. Cysteine compounds, notably L-acetyl-N-cysteine, is widely used in medicine, and should not prove a risk to fish consumers or to the environment at the concentrations proposed.

Ultrasound: Thomas & Gerritsen [13] described a method of eliminating all algae, not just the harmful ones. It is called *Aquasonic*, and works by transmitting ultrasonic vibrations into the water. It is claimed to kill all algae in a volume of 50,000 m³ with just a 15-Watt probe. This may take up to 2 weeks for the more refractory, filamentous algae. Already 2000 units are installed, mainly in Belgium and the Netherlands, primarily in water reservoirs and market gardens. The authors describe the device as "environmentally friendly", although some people might question this description of a technique that kills a whole trophic level. In its favour, however, its primary environmental impact stops when you switch the machine off. This device will probably be of most use in freshwater systems, or in those of limited extent. Particularly in view of their claimed ease of use and cheapness, quantitative investigations are required into the lethal and sublethal effects of ultrasound producers on the biota of water bodies.

Overview

For the first time, in this series of HAB meetings, there was an overview of mitigation techniques for fish farms, by Rensel [14]. He covered mitigation techniques using clays, and drew attention to the need for studies on the environmental effects of substances used for mitigation. Rensel's approach was very practical, and was also devoted to what I have called "management", particularly the design of net pens to minimise the effects of HABs, site selection, and the drawing up of contingency plans for when a HAB threatens and strikes. This presentation brought the same author's article in the IOC Manual [15] up to date, material which he is preparing for the second edition of the IOC Manual.

Cyanobacteria

For problems caused by cyanobacteria mitigation is already current, particularly in Australia. The mitigation itself can cause secondary problems, as explained by three groups of authors. Therefore, mitigation research is already at this second level. For drinking water, two presentations were made on the harmful effects that might arise from current mitigation techniques. Senogles *et al.* [16] told us that *Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii* is commonly found in drinking water in Queensland reservoirs. It produces a hepatotoxin, cylindrospermopsin, that is currently removed from the water by flocculation, sedimentation and filtration. Often, however, these techniques lyse the organisms. Methods of removal of the resulting dissolved cyanotoxin include oxidation by Cl_2 and ozone. UV treatment is also used, and is improved by adding TiO_2 . Müller *et al.* [17] reported research which suggests that if drinking water containing lysed cells of *Microcystis* or *Cylindrospermopsis* is treated with chlorine, then the chlorine reacts with organic matter liberated by this lysis to form toxic lower chlorinated phenols. Höger *et al.* [18] reported that ozonation reduces the level of cyanobacterial toxins in water containing *Microcystis* or *Oscillatoria*, where toxicity is measured by protein phosphatase inhibition (PPI). They found that this worked up to a certain cell density (e.g. 10^5 cells/ml for 1.0 mg O_3/L), above which toxicity actually increases due to lysis of cells and release of toxins. A residual level of 0.05 mg O_3/L was recommended in order to completely destroy this residual toxicity.

Possible techniques for the future

Effects of bacteria on harmful algae:

Bacteria have been found to infect and kill harmful algae. For instance, Ishio *et al.* [19] reported at Takamatsu that the bacterium *Vibrio alginifestans* killed at least 16 species of flagellate, although the harmful *Chattonella antiqua* manifests what appeared to be defensive behaviour. At Hobart, several communications mentioned algicidal bacteria. In particular, Mayali *et al.* found two strains lethal to *Gymnodinium breve* from Florida waters, and there were suggestions that it is promising as a future control agent.

Effects of parasites on harmful algae:

Norén *et al.* [20] reported that a recently described parasite, *Parvilucifera infectans*, related to the oyster-killing parasite, *Perkinsus*, was found in a natural population of *Dinophysis*. It has also been found to infect

Figure 1

other dinoflagellates, notably *Alexandrium*. The parasite has a high rate of lethal infection. The authors suggest that large-scale culture of this organism could be a useful adjunct to HAB mitigation, and would shift the plankton community towards non-toxic athecate dinoflagellates or other plankton groups.

Implications for the future

The rapidly changing proportions in the categories of papers (Fig. 1) at the International HAB meetings may represent a function of both 1) current interest (by the selection committee) in the subject and 2) novel interest. If so, then interest in mitigation *sensu lato* relative to HABs overall, appears to doubling every year. No doubt, the exponent will decline when mitigation *sensu stricto* takes its place, complementing monitoring and management programmes, to minimise the harmful effects of algal blooms world-wide. We may suggest that world-wide, and more locally, algal harm minimisation programmes will require mitigation as part of their umbrella of protection. This is rather like health programmes, which also employ monitoring (epidemiological studies), management (including health and hygiene education programmes), and mitigation (actual medical treatment, including some which have harmful side effects) for when infections strike despite the preventative measures taken.

In a large-scale experimental phase, once the first direct mitigation techniques have been

honed a little more, one could envisage stockpiles of substances, such as clays or cysteine compounds, strategically placed where problems could be foreseen. It would be important to have someone suitably trained to apply these products in the correct dilutions.

Concurrently, research, both practical and conceptual, needs to be encouraged into the effects of direct mitigation on the environment, particularly the plankton and the benthos. In some cases mitigation *sensu stricto*, might be expected to transfer ecological problems elsewhere, and perhaps introduce new problems. Recent suggestions to fertilise coastal zones, e.g., that of Markels [21], will no doubt increase the likelihood of seeking direct mitigation solutions, either openly or secretly, when the inevitable HABs arise. This would pose a risk of double-whammies [22]. Environmental damage caused by overzealous mitigation could come to be associated (perhaps rightly - it would depend on how things develop) with that caused by the aquaculture itself. One way to reduce the pressure to use mitigation will be to do good monitoring and management, and implement procedures according to their findings.

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mitigation and controls of HAB" by Hak-gyoon Kim.

He explained that fisheries loss could be mitigated, to some extent, by practical strategies such as "protect-HAB victim and "punish-HAB violator" system, even though there are difficult issues of predicting the extent and persistence.

With respect to punish-the-violator scheme, clay is the most efficient and least impact strategy to control harmful algae, and Korea reduced fisheries damages from US \$ 95 million in 1995 to US \$ 1.6 million in 1997 and US \$ 0.3 million in 1999 by this means. "Preliminary mesocosm studies of clay dispersal in Florida" by M. R. Sengco (WHOI) provided information on the deployment and effectiveness of clay dispersal; he reported that USA growing interest in the effects of clay for HAB control is growing. "Progress of studies on harmful algal blooms and mitigation with clays in China" by Zhiming Yu (Chinese

Academy of Sciences) emphasized that Van der Waals interactions during coagulation of kaolin on alga are important factors. Other Korean presentations described aspects of the effectiveness of clays for HAB control, methods of dispersal, and the impacts of clays on shellfish such as oyster, ark shell and abalone. Some positive effects of clays such as the extermination of Scuticociliata in cultured olive flounder by powdered clays, and increase of physiological functions of fish exposed to soil suspensions, were also reported.

Although it was generally accepted that clay removes HAB organisms, the issue highlighted in this symposium was the influence of clay dispersal on coastal ecosystems, and the potential risks of clays to the culture of marine organisms were discussed, especially the relationship between clay dispersion and alteration of the benthic habitats.

The symposium concluded by

recognizing the important effect of clay for HAB control, and noted the importance of collaboration among researchers in different HAB regions. Participants emphasized the importance of information sharing, and hope that this symposium will contribute to the future development of innovative research on HAB control.

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China Harmful Algal Bloom WebPages

Recently, with support from the Innovation Program of the Chinese Academy of Sciences, C-HAB Web Pages have been set up at <http://www.china-hab.ac.cn>, to provide basic knowledge to the public, summarize the main HAB occurrence in China, describe main HAB species, introduce research activities in China, and make links to international websites and projects. Recent HAB occurrences in China will be reported promptly at the Web Pages. The Web Pages have Chinese and English versions and are still under development.

◆ Mediterranean Sea

Production of domoic acid in another species of *Pseudo-nitzschia*: *P. multistriata* in the Gulf of Naples (Mediterranean Sea)

Species of the diatom genus *Pseudo-nitzschia* can attain high concentrations in coastal waters. The production of domoic acid (DA), the causative agent of Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning (ASP), is reported for at least eight species of this genus [1, 3]. *Pseudo-nitzschia* identification at the species level is not always possible in light microscopy and often requires SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy) and/or TEM (Transmission Electron Microscopy) investigations to detect the distinguishing

Figure 1. *Pseudo-nitzschia multistriata*, light micrograph; girdle view, showing the characteristic sigmoid shape of the cells.

morphological characters. Moreover, toxic and non-toxic strains seem to be present within the same 'morphospecies', suggesting a high genetic variability among strains, and/or differences in the factors controlling DA production. All this calls for accurate investigations aimed at correctly identifying *Pseudo-nitzschia* species and testing their potential toxicity.

A long-term phytoplankton monitoring program is conducted in the Gulf of Naples since 1984. The most abundant *Pseudo-nitzschia* species recorded in the Gulf are *P. delicatissima* and *P. pseudodelicatissima*. In recent years, *P. multistriata*, a species described from Japanese waters [4, 5], is recurrently recorded. This species, to our knowledge, has been never reported outside the type locality. Cells (38-50 mm long 2.8–3.8 mm wide) are characteristically sigmoid in girdle view (Fig. 1) and linear with pointed ends in

valve view (Fig. 2). TEM examination of several cultures revealed the ultrastructural features of this species (Fig. 3). The number of interstriae in 10 mm is 37-46, and the number of fibulae is 23-28. Two rows of circular poroids are present in each interstria and 11-12 poroids in 1 mm. A central interspace along the raphe is lacking.

Cultures of *P. delicatissima*, *P. pseudodelicatissima* and *P. multistriata* were collected in late exponential phase to test domoic acid content. Analyses were carried out according to the procedure in Hummert et al. [2] with an HPLC-MS API 165 PE SCIEX; the detection limit of the method is 3 ng DA absolute. Domoic acid was detected in the four cultures of *P. multistriata* with concentrations ranging from almost undetectable values in culture SZN-B27 to 0.645 pg cell⁻¹ in culture SZN-B28. No domoic acid was detected in *P. delicatissima* and *P. pseudodelicatissima* strains.

This is the first report of domoic-acid production for *P. multistriata* and the first report of a potential source of ASP in the Mediterranean Sea.

Figure 2. *Pseudo-nitzschia multistriata*, TEM micrograph of the whole cell in valve view.

Figure 3. *Pseudo-nitzschia multistriata*, TEM micrograph of the middle part of the valve, showing fibulae, interstriae and poroid arrangement.

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— Canada

Shellfish Harvest Area Closure due to Domoic Acid - Mill River, Prince Edward Island

In late September, mussel samples (*Mytilus edulis*) collected for the Shellfish Program by the Canadian Food Inspection Agency (CFIA) at Mill River, western PEI (Fig. 1), were found to contain the neurotoxin domoic acid (DA) at a level of 33 μg DA per gram (wet weight) of mussel tissue; the acceptable limit is 20 μg DA/g. Harvesting of molluscan shellfish from the Mill River area was therefore closed by Fisheries and Oceans Canada on September 22. This is the first closure due to DA in western PEI, and the first anywhere in PEI since 1994.

The DA toxin was first found in November, 1987, in mussels from Cardigan Bay, eastern PEI, in what was the world's first episode of Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning (ASP) [1]. At that time, the toxin was found to be produced by the pennate diatom *Pseudo-nitzschia multiseries*. Blooms of *Pseudo-nitzschia* species occur each autumn in PEI estuaries and bays, but since 1994, they have been less intense [2]. Reasons for the change in bloom intensity are still under investigation, but it is

Figure 1. Location of the September 2000 domoic-acid-producing *Pseudo-nitzschia multiseries* bloom in Prince Edward Island, resulting in closure of shellfish harvesting in Mill River. Previous closures have been in New London Bay and Cardigan Bay.

thought that meteorological conditions are in part responsible. The autumn 1987 toxic *P. multiseries* bloom was preceded by a prolonged dry period in summer, followed by an unusually rainy autumn [3]. This could have provided nutrients, via river runoff, to the estuaries.

Mill River is one of the few areas on PEI where water samples are not routinely collected for the enumeration of potentially toxic phytoplankton, because no previous incidences had been reported there. The first water sample was therefore only available

Figure 2. Scanning electron micrographs of *Pseudo-nitzschia multiseries*, taken from a sample collected in Mill River on September 23, 2000; the left panel shows a whole cell, and the right panel the detail of that cell, needed to confirm the species identity (images courtesy of Jim Ehrman, Digital Microscopy Facility, Mount Allison University, Sackville, New Brunswick).

one day after the closure, giving a cell count of about 220,000 *Pseudo-nitzschia* cells per litre. Scanning electron microscopy revealed only the toxin-producer *Pseudo-nitzschia multiseries* (Fig. 2); not one *P. pungens* cell was found in the sample. This is unusual, because blooms in late summer have usually been initiated with the non-toxic *Pseudo-nitzschia pungens* and then only later has the proportion of toxic *P. multiseries* increased [4]. Since 1994, *P. pungens* has become dominant, with few or no observed toxic *P. multiseries* cells, and consequently no DA in shellfish - until now.

It is likely that we had witnessed only the tail end of a short, but intense bloom. Mussel samples analyzed by the CFIA only one week prior to the closure revealed no detectable DA. The *P. multiseries* cells in the Mill River water sample appeared in poor

physiological condition. According to previous laboratory experiments, the majority of DA is produced when *P. multiseries* growth becomes limited by low concentrations of silicate or phosphate during stationary phase in batch culture [2]. Therefore, the cells in Mill River may have been highly toxic for a short period before the bloom crashed. Within 8 days of the peak in shellfish toxicity, only trace levels of DA (1 µg DA/g) remained in the mussels and the event was over. Shellfish harvesting resumed on October 6. The reasons for this short bloom, dominated by *P. multiseries*, are unknown. However, a rainy summer, combined with various nutrient sources upriver, may have provided opportune bloom conditions.

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◆ Gulf of California

First outbreak of *Cochlodinium polykrikoides* in the Gulf of California

From 15th to 28th of September 2000 several red patches were observed in the inner part of the coastal lagoon, La Enseñada de La Paz (24°10' - 24°47' N, 110°20' - 110°44' W). Surface samples were collected and fixed with Lugol. Because Lugol is not a good fixative agent for this dinoflagellate, many cells became rounded, contracted, or disrupted. The identification of this species was difficult and required examinations of live cells. Water samples were also taken for the determination of photosynthetic pigments. The dinoflagellate *Cochlodinium polykrikoides* (Fig. 1) was responsible for water discoloration. Although *C. polykrikoides* is cosmopolitan in warm and tropical waters, this is the first record of it in Gulf of California waters. The patches of *C. polykrikoides* were found mainly in shallow areas (1-4 m depth), within a temperature range from 29 to 31°C. Nutrient concentrations during this bloom were: 0.02 - 0.90 µM NO₂+NO₃, 0.16 - 2.2 µM PO₄, and 1.0 - 35.36 µM SiO₄. Most cells of *C. polykrikoides* formed chains of four, rarely two. Cell density ranged from 360 x 10³ to 7.05 x 10⁶ *Cochlodinium*/L. Chlorophyll *a* concentration was 2.7 to 56.8 mg/m³. *C. polykrikoides* is a species that kills fish in Korea [1], but few dead fish were associated with this event. This bloom occurred close to several fish and shrimp-culture ponds, and

one of the ponds was infested with *Cochlodinium*. A total of 27 dead fish were found in the fish-pond, possibly caused by the dinoflagellate. There are no earlier records of *C. polykrikoides* in this area, but a *Cochlodinium* sp bloom has been recorded off Manzanillo, México [2]. Hydrographical and phytoplankton monitoring programs are necessary to prevent mortality marine animals, particularly cage species of economic interest. Work is in hand to obtain cultures of this species, and to evaluate its toxicity.

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Figure 1. Light microscopy photograph of *Cochlodinium polykrikoides*

◆ Morocco

Blooms of *Prymnesium parvum* associated with fish mortalities in a hypereutrophic brackish lake in Morocco.

Prymnesium parvum N. Carter

In Morocco, harmful algae blooms studied so far have been caused by dinoflagellates which on the Atlantic and Mediterranean coasts [1], and by cyanobacteria in several lakes and reservoirs [2]. During a recent hydrobiological survey of Oued Mellah reservoir (Fig. 1; Table 1), autumnal Chrysophycean blooms of *Prymnesium parvum* occurred in November - December 1998 and September - October 1999. This was the first event of this kind recorded in Moroccan waters. The same site is also characterised by cyanobacterial blooms of *Microcystis ichthyoblabe* and *Aphanizomenon flos aquae* in spring and summer [3].

During the *P. parvum* proliferation, the water was characterised by moderate temperatures (15 – 23.5°C), elevated salinity (8.6 – 12.64 ‰), alkaline pH (7.67 – 9.04), a high content of organic matter (4.4 – 8.6

Table 1. General characteristics of Oued Mellah lake – reservoir.

Lake.....	Oued Mellah reservoir
Date of construction.....	1928-1931
Geographical situation..	33°30'N - 07°20'W - 25 km north of Casablanca
River.....	Oued Mellah
Total capacity.....	18 Mm ³
Useful capacity.....	8,8 Mm ³
Surface.....	250 ha
Maximum depth.....	9 m
Normal elevation.....	101,75 NGM
Bioclimate.....	Semi-arid Thermomediterranean with hot winter
Catchment geology.....	Primary schist surmounted by gréso-maghrébiennne tile with triassic saliferous clays and altered basalts.
Use.....	Domestic water production - irrigation - electricity - Fishing and recreation
Ecological interest.....	National Biological and Ecological Interest Site (BEIS n°H8).

mgO₂.L⁻¹), elevated concentrations of total nitrogen (1,69 - 3,77 mg.L⁻¹), limited concentrations of nitrates (78.5 – 195.5 µg.L⁻¹) and undetectable amounts of orthophosphates. The chlorophyll a concentration (105.65 – 322.1 µg.L⁻¹) was mainly due to *P. parvum*, that dominated the phytoplankton (34 to 80% of total biomass). Cell counts were very high with maxima of 148x10⁶ cells.L⁻¹ in 1998 and 169x10⁶ cells.L⁻¹ in 1999. Such cell concentrations impart a yellow-gold colour to the water which is characteristic of haptophycean blooms.

Blooms of this species cause extensive fish mortalities (carps, barbels, eels, sun-poles, gambusia...) (see photograph), and also kill other animals such as shrimps, bivalves and other invertebrates. The kinetics of *P. parvum* development showed that fish mortality began at the end of the growth phase and continued during the stationary phase of the 1998 and 1999 blooms. *P. parvum* is known to cause toxic blooms with catastrophic fish-kills in brackish waters in Europe, the Middle East, Ukraine, USA and Australia [4, 5]. Recently, Igarashi et al. [6] isolated and elucidated the structure of the causative ichthyotoxic and haemolytic compounds prymnesin-1 and prymnesin-2 from cultivated cells of *P. parvum*. Prymnesins show diverse biological activities including mouse toxicity, ichthyotoxicity, cytotoxicity and antibacterial activity [7,8].

In addition to the economic and ecological damages caused by these mortalities, the Oued Mellah lake lost its touristic value (Picnics, excursions, sport fishing, sailing...). These blooms constitute a high sanitary risk for the riparian population for two reasons, on one hand because of the deterioration of water quality, and on the other hand because of the uncontrolled commercialisation of large quantities of dying fish collected from the banks. Further autoecological and toxicological studies of isolated strains of *P. parvum* are in progress.

Figure 1. Geographic situation of Oued Mellah reservoir

Fish mortality caused by *Prymnesium parvum* bloom in Oued Mellah reservoir (November 1998)

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◆ British Isles

A Key for the identification of blue-green algae of the British Isles

Eutrophication and blue-green algae (cyanobacteria)

Eutrophication is recognised by the Environment Agency of England and Wales as a national water quality issue and has become more widespread in recent decades, resulting in deterioration of the aquatic environment and serious problems for water-use. Cyanobacteria (blue-green algae) are a major recognised symptom of eutrophication, and generally occur during warm, dry summers, with plenty of sunshine and little wind mixing, although blooms can also occur during other periods. Cyanobacterial blooms and scums are natural features of many waterbodies and are likely to remain so, although successful eutrophication control strategies may limit the extent of their development.

Cyanobacterial toxicity

Cyanobacteria are capable of producing severely toxic chemicals potentially resulting in deleterious health effects, and even death in fish, livestock, pets and humans. Blooms may also have serious negative economic consequences for aquaculture (fish and shellfisheries).

Toxicity assessments of cyanobacterial scums/blooms continue to indicate a high incidence of toxicity (more than two-thirds of samples analysed are toxic). The Environment Agency, therefore, continues to adopt a precautionary approach, recognising the need to regard all cyanobacteria species and strains as

capable of producing toxins, and hence to regard cyanobacterial populations as a threat to human and animal health and safety.

Environment Agency monitoring protocol

Monitoring of affected sites was extensive during the incidents of 1989 and 1990, when large cyanobacterial blooms were identified in UK inland waters, and intensive programmes were adopted for some sites. Since then, a reactive monitoring programme has been advocated, principally to cater for those water body owners and users who had not previously contacted the Agency. This approach reduced the earlier monitoring effort, allowing resources to be diverted into eutrophication control developments (aimed at reducing blue-green algal problems) – see www.environment-agency.gov.uk, 'Aquatic Eutrophication in England and Wales: a proposed management strategy' consultation document.

The Agency's position

The lack of suitable reference books for accurate naming of blue-green algae has been a major hindrance to algological work within the Environment Agency. Whilst there are both beginner's guides and specialised taxonomic works (usually in foreign languages), a practical blue-green algal flora has not been available.

A collaborative project was set-up with the University of Durham to produce a key

for identification of blue-green algae from the British Isles to assist Agency staff engaged in monitoring work. The principal output is a computer-based interactive system built from LucID Professional, a specialised computer package for developing biological identification systems. The system was produced initially in CD-ROM format and has subsequently been made available nationally to Agency ecologists through the computer network on the Windows desktop.

The CD-ROM was officially launched by the Environment Agency and University of Durham on 30 May 2000.

In the future, it is hoped that following the success of this collaborative project there will be additional keys in CD-ROM format for other algal groups, adopting the LucID interactive system.

Background information

The key aids the identification of any blue-green algal sample collected in the British Isles. It includes 320 species in 65 genera of freshwater, terrestrial and marine blue-green algae, and contains many illustrations and colour images together with species descriptions. Freshwater and terrestrial species follow the Coded list of freshwater algae of the British Isles incorporating recent taxonomic developments. The key was based on LucID Professional software developed at the University of Queensland, Australia and operates as a multi-access key with the user answering questions for whatever information

they possess about the sample. LucID suggests possible names, and the user can then check the sample against the suggested species descriptions and images

Copies of R&D Technical Report E84, providing explanation of the LucID key and taxonomic accounts of genera, and R&D Technical Summary leaflet ES83 are available internally from the Regional Environment Agency Libraries/Management Support Officers and externally from WRc plc.

Contacts

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◆ North Sea

Chattonella sp. bloom in North Sea, spring 2000

Detection of the bloom

An extensive bloom caused by two raphidophytes, *Chattonella*-like cells, occurred from the German Bight almost to north Skagen between late April and the first half of May. On the 2 and 15 May, 2000, two helicopter flights sampled along the North Sea coast of Schleswig-Holstein. On the first flight we found reddish discolouration in the coastal waters, 10 km off Sylt Island. The dominant species was *Chattonella* sp with more than 10 million cells per liter mixed with *Chattonella* cf. *verruculosa* and another unknown flagellate on the first sampling date. The corresponding chlorophyll concentration was 80.17 µg/l. On a routine cruise in April, Norwegian colleagues observed *Chattonella* cf. *verruculosa* with a concentration of 25-30 millions cells per litre, 10-18 kilometer off the coast of Esbjerg, Denmark on the 19-20 April 2000. On 4 May, Viborg County took samples about 20 km off Hanstholm and found 8.7-11 million *Chattonella* cells per liter. On 5 May, 1.8 million *Chattonella*-like cells per liter were found 10 km off Hirtshals by Danish scientists (Peter Henriksen, personal communication). On 15 May, *Chattonella* sp. Was still present, but the bloom had disappeared. This large bloom was also detected by MOS and SeaWiFS satellite images in cloud free conditions (Fig. 1). Peak concentrations may have been subsurface, especially in the sunny weather condition and not visible from the satellite.

Light microscope observations

1. *Chattonella* sp. (Fig. 2a)

Living cells are 12 - 23 µm long, of variable size, ovoid to irregularly ovoid, unlike

Figure 1. *Chattonella* sp. bloom was detected by two satellite sensors

Chattonella verruculosa; numerous, small chloroplasts; with two flagella, the shorter one as long as cell body, pulling the cell forward, pointed, slightly curved, in the swimming direction, the longer one twice cell length, trailing, close to the cell body, sometimes hidden.

The cells have mucocysts, and are phototactic. Living cells are very sensitive. They can die in a few minutes under light microscope. They stop swimming and lose flagella just before dying. Then the shape of the body changes immediately. Lugol-fixed cells usually lose their original cell-shape or break. However chloroplasts are visible and accumulated.

2. Unknown flagellate (Fig. 2b)

Living cells are 18-22 µm diameter, slightly flattened and roughly heart-shaped, flagella insertion marked by strong intrusion; numerous, irregularly plate-shaped chloroplasts; one flagella, about 3 times cell length; swimming behavior turning, sometimes stop, then continue; flagellum pushes cell forward. Swimming behavior is distinct from that of *Chattonella* species. Cells have big mucocysts, protruding from cell surface. Sometimes, during swimming or resting, the cells jumps straight forward, maybe caused by ejectosomes?

Fig.2. A. *Chattonella* sp. (living cells), 12-24 μm in length; B. Unknown flagellates, mucocysts are clearly visible (living cells), 18-22 μm in length

Fish kill and toxicity

Toxic *Chattonella* species are well known for fish killing in Japanese waters, where they have been observed since 1969. In European waters, *Chattonella antiqua* and *Chattonella marina* were first recorded in Netherlands coastal waters in 1991 [4]. A *Chattonella* cf. *verruculosa* bloom was first recorded in the North Sea in 1998 and killed more than 400 t of cultured salmon in southern Norway as well as some wild fish [5]. During the bloom this year, some dead herring and trout were found in Danish waters, which might be associated with this species (Peter Henriksen, pers. comm.). The killing mechanism of *Chattonella* to fish is not clear yet. It may be related both to physical clogging of gills and to toxins. The toxicity of raphidophytes, though not yet fully

investigated, seems to originate from neurotoxins as known from *C. antiqua* and *C. marina* [3].

Environmental aspects

The history of *Chattonella* in the North Sea is short, and it is not known whether these toxic raphidophytes are exotic or indigenous to European waters [1]. Because the cells are so small, fragile and difficult to preserve, they might be overlooked if cell density is low. On the other hand, *Chattonella* sp. was never found in such high cell concentrations in this area before 1998. It seems that they have now established a niche and have the potential to recur and form extensive blooms in the North Sea. Does this phenomenon indicate some kind of environmental change?

Acknowledgement

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◆ Northwestern Atlantic

A parasite of *Dinophysis acuminata* in northwestern Atlantic

At the International Conference on Harmful Algal Blooms in Tasmania last February, Noren, Moestrup and Rehnstam-Holm presented their elegant work on the identity and life cycle of a highly infective flagellate, the parasite *Parvilucifera infectans*, of the newly introduced phylum Perkinsozoa. They astutely combined ultrastructural observations and molecular data. A photograph of an infected *Dinophysis norvegica* on their poster and in their talk immediately caught my eye and led me to question whether this parasite sporangium could correspond to the large circular inclusions sometimes found in *D. acuminata* in coastal Rhode Island waters. Later on at the meeting, my suspicions came closer to certainty when Chretiennot-Dinet showed fabulous video recordings of parasitic zoospores of a very similar, perhaps identical (?), dinoflagellate-specific parasite

from French coastal waters (part of this recording can be viewed from a CD-ROM available in a special issue of *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, [1], or on line at <http://www.academicpress.com/www/journal/ec/suppmat/contents.htm>). Both groups of researchers wondered about the geographic distribution of these parasites outside western European waters. The present note reports on my observations in northeastern US waters of *D. acuminata* with inclusions suspected to correspond to or be affiliated with the above parasite(s).

In coastal embayments around Narragansett Bay, Rhode Island, significant populations of *D. acuminata* develop between May and October with peaks commonly occurring in June and/or July, especially at times of strong water column stratification [2]. Over the years, weekly sampling of this dinoflagellate from

Figure 1. Single large circular inclusion (arrow) inside *Dinophysis acuminata* similar to a developing sporangium of the parasite *Parvilucifera infectans* (Greenwich Cove, July 1 1995). Bright field microscopy.

Figure 2. Reticulate chloroplasts of a healthy *D. acuminata*. Epifluorescence microscopy.

Greenwich Cove (41°39.5'N, 71°27'W) has revealed a wide range of variations (number and size) in cellular inclusions observed both by light and epifluorescence microscopy. Except for some conspicuously large circular inclusions, most of the observed variations can usually be attributed either to volume changes in the pusular system or to the occasional presence of food vacuoles. It now appears very likely that the "large circular inclusions" seen in *D. acuminata* correspond to parasitic sporangia. My first observation of these large inclusions dates back to early July 1995, when *D. acuminata* reached 20,000 cells L⁻¹; a small proportion of cells (ca. 2%) harbored such round bodies (Fig. 1). Again toward the end of July 1999, large inclusions (one or two per cell) were recorded inside *D. acuminata*, but this time, some tiny swimmers were actively swimming inside as well as outside one of them, a particularly large inclusion within an otherwise almost empty *Dinophysis* theca. Unaware of the then unpublished findings of Noren and Erard-Le Denn and colleagues [1, 3], I questioned the nature of these round bodies, as others had done before [4].

When under blue excitation in epifluorescence microscopy, a healthy photosynthetic *D. acuminata* displays a flamboyant yellow-orange stellate to reticulate chloroplast (Fig. 2); however, the

occasional "grape- or bead-like" appearance of certain chloroplasts has been puzzling. Variations in previous light history or nutrient status of the cells could be invoked but our inability to establish long-term culture of this dinoflagellate limits or complicates testing basic hypotheses. Noren *et al.* [3] report on the "granular appearance of the chloroplast" upon infection of *D. norvegica*. Thus parasitic infection may also account for some of the variation observed in the shape and size of the chloroplast. Interestingly, in July 1995, most *D. acuminata* displayed one or two chloroplasts looking like "clumps of grapes" (Fig. 3).

My observations need detailed ultrastructural and molecular analyses before the large inclusions in *D. acuminata* on this side of the Atlantic can be attributed with certainty to *P. infectans* or a close relative. However, taken all together and in light of the works mentioned above, these observations would suggest a parasitic nature for the inclusions.

The recognition that various pathogens may significantly contribute to regulation of protistan population dynamics has gained momentum in the past decade and has revived the idea that harmful algal blooms may be controlled via biological means [1, 3, 5]. Although the newly described potential candidate, the water-borne parasite *P. infectans*, is culturable and so far appears dinoflagellate-specific, it must be remembered that results of infection studies have been published on just a few diatoms and one raphidophyte, besides dinoflagellates. Hence many questions remain, mostly pertaining to conditions of infection, list of susceptible hosts (undesirable

Figure 3. *Beady* chloroplasts of a *D. acuminata* cell during the putative parasitic episode (July 1 1995). Epifluorescence microscopy

as well as desirable ones), effects of broad manipulations of food web dynamics and unintentional introduction into non-target areas. Erring on the side of caution would be prudent.

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GEOHAB

The emerging new science programme sponsored by SCOR and IOC on the Global Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms (GEOHAB) will soon publish its Science Plan (SP). The SP has been prepared by the IOC-SCOR Scientific Steering Committee (SSC) for GEOHAB. The SP was presented to, and adopted by, the SCOR General Meeting in October 2000 pending editorial changes. At a meeting of the SSC in La Paz, Mexico, 13-17 November 2000, the SP was revised based on the comments and advice of three independent reviewers appointed by SCOR

The SP is built around five programme elements: Biogeography and Biodiversity;

Adaptive Strategies, Nutrients and Eutrophication; Ecosystem Processes; Observation and Modelling.

The SP will be available on World Wide Web for comments from the scientific community around 1 March 2001, and is expected to be published in April 2001.

The next step is development of an implementation plan for the Programme. The Implementation Plan (IP) will describe how the programme will approach the objectives of the SP, of which the primary one is to foster international research. This requires a coordinating framework to link existing national programmes and encourage and initiate more scientific interest in HABs.

The IP will be cross-cutting in approach, but will address each defined objective of the SP and will describe the actions required to achieve it. The IP will also consider the extent to which the objectives are already being undertaken, or standards are being set, by existing national programmes and how GEOHAB can help in international coordination. The development of the IP will require strong interaction with the scientific community and the SSC is charged with taking initiative for outreach activities in order to ensure such involvement.

The SSC, IOC, and SCOR are endeavoring to establish an International Project Office (IPO) to help implement

(Cont'd from p. 12)

GEOHAB. Funding for the IPO is being sought, and an official offer for partial support has been received. A major task of the SSC, SCOR, and IOC is to raise the remaining funding to establish the IPO.

You can follow the development of GEOHAB and in due time have access to the SP at <http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/GEOHAB.htm>, or contact the Chair of the GEOHAB SSC Dr. Patrick Gentien, CREMA, B.P. 5, 17137 L'Houmeau, FRANCE,

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The ICES/IOC Working Group on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics will meet in Dublin, Ireland, from 12B16 March 2001 to update the harmful algae event database (HAEDAT). It will also examine possible ways of analysing historical data and fossil records, and evaluate and assess the use of remote sensing and *in situ* optical sensing technology in HAB dynamics studies. There will be discussions of the potential sensitivity of HABs to climate changes; review of the implementation of GEOHAB relevant research in the ICES area; and preparation of a resolution for a workshop, possibly co-sponsored by regional programmes such as GEOHAB, GLOBEC and GOOS, on «Real Time Observation Systems applied to Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics Studies and Global Ecosystem Functioning».

A Study Group on GEOHAB Implementation in the Baltic will meet in Dublin, Ireland from 12B13 March 2001 to create a plan for the implementation of GEOHAB in the Baltic Sea. SCOR and IOC will be invited to co-sponsor the Study Group. *Scientist from outside the North Atlantic (ICES area), can also join the WGABD as it is IOC co-sponsored. Inquiries can be made to the Chair of the two groups, Dr. Kaisa Kononen, Maj and Tor Nessling Foundation, P. Hesperiankatu 3 A 4, FIN-00260 HELSINKI, FINLAND, Fax: +358-9-406 684, E-mail: Kaisa.Kononen@nessling.fi*

Mónica Lion is since 15 May 2000 head of the "IOC-IEO Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae" in Vigo, Spain. Mónica has been part of HAB community since 1996 when she started as a PhD student in the Centro de Investigaciones Marinas (Xunta de Galicia) in Vilanova de Arousa, under the guidance of Dr. J. Blanco. In her new job, she relies on the valuable help of all the HAB staff in the Instituto Español de Oceanografía and other experts from the Galician research laboratories working on different HAB aspects, to carry out training, assessment and communication activities according to the priorities of the IOC-IPHAB, with special attention to Latin American countries.

The main activities of the Vigo Centre are: HAB related research and managerial questions; development and maintenance of the IOC-ICES HAEDAT (Harmful Algae

Events) data-base; compilation and co-edition of "Harmful Algae News"; organization of annual international training courses on "Toxic Phytoplankton and Phycotoxins"; assistance in development and implementation of relevant IOC HAB programme activities; free-of-charge dissemination of manuals, reports, conference proceedings etc. to Spanish and Latinamerican institutions; databases of Iberoamerican experts, a bibliography, etc.

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New Staff in the IOC-HAB programme

Ole Vestergaard joined the IOC Secretariat in Paris 1 April 2000. He is seconded to the IOC by Denmark as an Associate Expert. He will devote half of his time to the IOC HAB Programme. His responsibilities are development, co-ordination, and administrative back-up of the HAB Programme at IOC Headquarters in Paris. He works in close contact with the IOC HAB Science and Communication Centres in Copenhagen and Vigo. As a biologist he has been working with various aspects of aquatic ecology. Before joining the IOC he worked at the University of Copenhagen doing research on macroalgae diversity and

distribution patterns in marine and brackish waters. He has also been working with Arctic marine phytoplankton and with monitoring and environmental assessments of aquatic ecosystems. Besides working for the HAB Programme, Ole also functions as Technical Secretary for the Global Coral Reef Monitoring Network (GCRMN), and a number of other IOC science programs.

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International Ballast Water Treatment Symposium & Workshop

The International Maritime Organization (IMO), with funding provided by the Global Environment Facility (GEF) through the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), has initiated the Global Ballast Water Management Programme (GloBallast).

This programme is aimed at reducing the transfer of harmful marine species in ships' ballast water, by assisting developing countries to implement existing IMO voluntary *Guidelines for the control and management of ships' ballast water to minimize the transfer of harmful aquatic*

limit its applicability, and the fact that translocation of species can still occur even when a vessel has been able to fully implement ballast exchange/reballasting at sea.

It is therefore extremely important that alternative, effective ballast water management and/or treatment methods are developed as soon as possible, to replace reballasting at sea. Significant research and development (R&D) efforts are underway by a number of scientific and engineering research establishments around the world,

including the Ballast Water Working Group of IMO's Marine Environment Protection Committee (MEPC), have identified the current lack of such standards and criteria as the single largest obstacle to finding a solution to the problem of marine organism transfers in ballast water.

In addition, many groups are working in isolation from each other. There are no formal mechanisms in place to ensure effective lines of communication between IMO, the R&D community, governments and ship designers, builders and owners on ballast

organisms and pathogens (Assembly Resolution A.868(20)), and to prepare for the anticipated introduction of an international legal instrument on ballast water management currently being developed by IMO member countries.

The Need for and Purpose of the Symposium & Workshop

A core objective of the GloBallast programme is to assist developing countries to implement the existing IMO voluntary guidelines on ballast water management. The main management measure recommended under these guidelines is ballast exchange/reballasting at sea. It is widely recognized that this approach has many limitations, including serious safety considerations that

aimed at developing a more complete solution to the problem. All of these possibilities currently require significant further research effort. Major barriers still exist in scaling these various technologies to deal effectively with the huge quantities of ballast water carried by large ships (e.g. about 60,000 tonnes of ballast water on a 200,000 dwt bulk carrier). Treatment options must not interfere unduly with the safe and economical operation of the ship and must consider ship design limitations.

One of the problems currently faced by the global R&D and shipping community is that apart from the general criteria above, there are currently no internationally agreed and approved standards and criteria for the evaluation and approval of new ballast water treatment systems that are developed.

Most parties involved in the ballast water

water treatment issues. These are vital if the R&D effort is to succeed.

To help address this situation, the GloBallast Programme Coordination Unit (PCU) is organizing an international symposium 26-27 March 2001 (open) and workshop 28-30 March 2001 (invitation only) on ballast water treatment

Further information

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◆ Spain

IOC-AECI- IEO IV Course on Toxic Microalgae and Marine Phycotoxins

Once again, the IOC-IEO Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae organized a Course on "Toxic Microalgae and Marine Phycotoxins" from 1-17 June 2000, at the Instituto Español de Oceanografía (IEO) in Vigo, Spain. It was sponsored by the IOC, the Agencia Española de Cooperación Internacional (AECI) and the IEO.

Thirteen scientists from different countries (Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Cuba, Ecuador, Guatemala, Haiti, Mexico, Italy, Puerto Rico, Venezuela) participated in the course that is part of the training activities included in the Harmful Algal Bloom Programme of IOC. The purpose of the course was to impart theoretical and practical knowledge about four aspects of toxic microalgae: Cultures, Taxonomy, Toxin determination and Benthic harmful microalgae.

All participants were invited to work with their own samples and presented a status report on harmful algal blooms in their countries. Complementing these activities, some visits to local research laboratories working with HAB were programmed.

Lectures were given by staff from IEO, Instituto de Investigaciones Marinas (IIM-

CSIC), European Union Reference Laboratory on Marine Biotoxins, Centro de Control de Calidade do Medio Mariño and Centro de Investigacions Mariñas (Xunta de Galicia), ANFACO-CECOPESCA and Universities of Vigo and Santiago de Compostela.

The general impression of the course was very positive and we hope it will enable

the participants to improve their capabilities and get valuable contacts for future collaborations.

This IOC training course is organized every year. Additional information can be required from "IOC-IEO Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae" (fax +34 986 492003 or e-mail: vigohab@vi.ieo.es)

◆ Europe

BIOHAB, A European Initiative

Biological control of Harmful Algal blooms in European coastal waters (BIOHAB) is a new EU research program with participants from 7 European institutes. It started March 2000 and will continue for 3 years. BIOHAB addresses one of the key issues of pollution, namely nutrients. Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) occur in many European marine waters and may have increased in frequency with increased nutrient inputs from land.

The overall objective of BIOHAB is to determine the interplay between (anthropogenic) eutrophication and biological control of the losses and gains to HAB populations. The ultimate goal is to find ways to manage algal blooms in European coastal waters so that harmful species are avoided or at least that their

negative effects are minimised. The project involves co-operation between several European countries, representing distinctly differing regions (the eutrophic North Sea, the low salinity Baltic, the oligotrophic Norwegian Sea, and the P-limited Mediterranean).

The scientific objectives are (1) To determine the susceptibility of HABs to biological control such as grazing (copepods, ciliates, hetero- and mixotrophic dinoflagellates) and infection (virus, bacteria, parasites) when growing under nutrient deficient and sufficient conditions. (2) Investigate the roles of HAB infochemicals in relation to grazing and infection. (3) To examine the general and unique patterns of growth and decline of HAB-species in

various coastal regions. (4) To develop a generic or species-specific model for the development of HABs and their mitigation. (5) To obtain and grow HAB species-specific pathogens (viruses, bacteria, parasites) with potential to control HABs.

The Helsinki (HELCOM) and Oslo Paris (OPARCOM) Commissions have the primary task to protect the marine environments of the Baltic and North Seas. BIOHAB aims to improve knowledge of biological factors affecting key HAB-species, and may indicate potential ways to control HABs.

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New home for the Phycotoxins mailing list

For the past 30 months, PHYCOTOXINS has been residing on the Listquest.com servers but the company encountered unspecified difficulties and ceased most services on September 27. As we could not establish contact with the company by various means, about ten days passed before we decided the problems were terminal. A new service, using LISTSERV software, was launched using Canadian Food Inspection Agency (CFIA) servers on October 12. Phycotoxins continues to be managed by Don Richard (richarddj@em.agr.ca) of the CFIA in New Brunswick, Canada with backup support by Bill Silvert (wsilvert@ipimar.pt) at Instituto Nacional de Investigação das Pescas in Lisbon, Portugal.

There are currently about 550 subscribers throughout the world. Topics include the reporting of bloom events, fish kills, poisonings, conferences and workshops announcements, requests for information, job postings (but not requests for employment), and other issues related to phycotoxins. The relocation and

formatting of the archives is a work-in-progress but should be completed in the near future. To join the phycotoxins list, send an e-mail to listserv@www.agr.ca with the line «**subscribe phycotoxins yourfirstname yourlastname**» in the body of your message. Should you require assistance, send the command «**info refcard**» to the same address or contact the owner at richarddj@em.agr.ca. Mailing lists rely on the members for information so please post relevant articles as you see fit. The list will be moderated for the next few months so as to keep errors and spam to a minimum.

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HAB Capacity building

In August 2000, the Seventh International IOC-DANIDA Training Course on the Taxonomy and Biology of Harmful Algae was held at the IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae at the Botanical Institute, University of Copenhagen. Over the years, the courses have in addition to provision of specific training established many fruitful working contacts and networks, some of which have resulted in cooperative research projects. The courses have benefited enormously from the close and successful cooperation between the Universities of Copenhagen, Tokyo, Nagasaki, Lund, Jena, Rhode Island, and the Spanish Institute of Oceanography, in composing the programme and providing the lecturers. The first course took place in 1993,

and it has for some time been a wish from former participants who are still very active in HAB research, to have an opportunity to upgrade and up-date their knowledge even further. The IOC will accommodate this wish in 2001 by introducing a high level advanced HAB identification course with special focus on related techniques and difficult taxonomic groups. The details of the programme will be decided in cooperation with the selected trainees. The course will be open both former course participants and other applicants with the similar background. In 2001 the introductory level to HAB species identification will be addressed at regional courses. The IOC HAB training courses in 2001 will be announced early 2001 at <http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/train.htm>

Future events

JUNE 2002

4th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MOLLUSCAN SHELLFISH SAFETY, Santiago de Compostela, Galicia, Spain, 4-8 June 2002. Hosted by "Centro de Investigacions Mariñas" (Marine Research Centre) and "Centro de Control da Calidade do Medio Mariño" (Galician Monitoring Centre). The sessions will be dealing with: microbiological contamination; chemical contamination and bioaccumulation; harmful and toxic algal events; shellfish contamination by marine biotoxins; depuration; management and mitigation; water quality at harvesting sites; public health; epidemiology and toxicology; monitoring, quality assurance programmes and regulatory controls; and allergies associated with shellfish consumption. Contact: ICMSS, c/o Dr Antonio Villalba. Fax: +34 986 506788; E-mail: villalba@cimacoron.org

OCTOBER 2001

The JOINT ASSEMBLY OF THE INTERNATIONAL ASSOCIATION FOR THE PHYSICAL SCIENCES OF THE OCEANS (IAPSO) AND THE INTERNATIONAL ASSOCIATION FOR BIOLOGICAL OCEANOGRAPHY (IABO), to be held in Mar del Plata, Argentina, on 21 - 28 October 2001, with Joint Symposia of the International Association of Meteorology and Atmospheric Sciences (IAMAS), the World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE), the Climate Variability and Predictability Program (CLIVAR), the Joint Global Ocean Flux Study (JGOFS), the Global Ocean Ecosystems Dynamics Program (GLOBEC), and the International Association of Geodesy (IAG), has issued a call for papers. Abstracts must be submitted electronically, and must be in the format given on the Joint Assembly Web page at http://www.criba.edu.ar/2001_ocean (note that there is an underline between «2001» and «ocean» in the URL address).

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

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